

FATIGUE DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN GLASS/EPOXY LAMINATES WITH STRESS CONCENTRATIONS: EXPERIMENTS AND MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

The work illustrates a fatigue design strategy, based on the physics of the damage evolution, developed by the Composite Group at the University of Padova over the last few years. After a brief introduction, where the motivations of the work are analyzed, examples of damage mechanisms at the macro- and micro-scale are discussed. Then the models for the quantitative description of these mechanisms are illustrated, together with experimental validation. Eventually, the application of the modelling framework to the prediction of the damage evolution in composite plate with central hole is presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Most structural components made from composite materials are subjected to cyclic loading during their service life. This can result in the progressive evolution of damage, a corresponding loss of stiffness, and, ultimately, catastrophic failure. Designing against fatigue is therefore essential to enhance the reliability of composite structural components across a wide range of applications.

To address the growing need for fatigue-resistant composite design tools, the authors have spent several years developing a comprehensive design framework. This framework aims to predict the initiation of damage, its progression, and the final failure of composite laminates under cyclic loading conditions.

In the context of composite materials, characterized by a multitude of progressive damage mechanisms, "design against fatigue" can take on different meanings, depending on the requirements of the component. These include:

- i) Design to prevent crack initiation;
- ii) Design to prevent excessive stiffness degradation (damage-tolerant design);
- iii) Design to prevent final failure.

As will be discussed in more detail later, damage development in composite laminates involves multiscale and hierarchical processes. These range from micro-scale damage initiation to the growth of macro-cracks and delamination, ultimately resulting in failure. The nature of these mechanisms depends on several factors, including the constituent materials, laminate lay-up, loading type, and multi-axial stress conditions [1].

To effectively tackle such a complex problem and deliver reliable design methods for each of the aforementioned objectives, it is necessary to develop models based on the physical damage mechanisms occurring at various length scales [1]. These models must then be integrated into a multiscale, multi-mechanism design strategy that must be also efficient and flexible to comply with real component design and industrial workflows.

The following sections present representative examples of the key mechanisms that drive laminate degradation and failure under cyclic loading. Subsequently, the proposed modelling strategy is introduced and an application on notched laminates is presented.

2 FATIGUE DAMAGE MECHANICS

The damage evolution in composite materials is a multiscale and hierarchical process, involving several mechanisms at different length scales. In this work, the macro-scale is related to the ply and laminate level, whereas the micro-scale is relevant to the fiber diameter and the inter-fiber spacing.

As widely proved in the literature (see Refs. [2-6] among the others), the first macro-scale damage event in a multidirectional laminate is represented by the initiation of off-axis cracks that involve the entire thickness of a ply and propagate along the fiber direction. The crack density increases during the lifetime and a saturation condition is reached after a certain number of cycles. The second observable mechanism, in chronological order, is represented by delamination. A delamination initiates from the tips of the off-axis cracks at the interface with confining layers and propagates in a direction normal to the off-axis cracks. These two mechanisms are not directly responsible for the laminate failure but cause a significant loss of stiffness that must be correctly predicted if a damage tolerant design approach is adopted. An example of the damage evolution, highlighting the initiation and propagation of multiple off-axis cracks, is shown in Figure 1.

The final failure is eventually typically controlled by the main load bearing plies, which means that it is caused by the failure of the 0° -oriented fibers.

Fig. 1. Example of fatigue damage evolution and failure in a $[0/60_2/0/-60_2]_s$ laminate [6]

The mentioned macro-scale damage events have their precursors and interaction at the microscale, in the form of microcracks, fiber-matrix debonds and fiber breaks. In a damage-based approach, criteria for predicting the onset and evolution of the macroscopic damage modes should be, thus, based on the micro-scale damage mechanisms.

For instance, the micro-scale damage process leading to an off-axis crack formation consists in the initiation and growth of matrix micro-cracks, which eventually coalesce forming the off-axis crack (Figure 2). This is relevant to local stress states characterized by a sufficiently high $\lambda_{12}=\sigma_6/\sigma_2$ (shear to transverse stress ratio). For instance, Figure 2 shows such micro-cracks, in the external 45° ply of a $[45/-45/0]_s$ glass/epoxy laminate under tension/tension fatigue [7]. These micro cracks were shown to be normal to the Local Maximum Principal Stress (LMPS) in the matrix, that was then considered as the effective stress to be used for predicting crack formation in such conditions [8].

If the stress state in a ply is such that the in-plane stress component σ_6 is zero, it was proved [9] that the local stress state in the matrix, close to the fiber-matrix interface, is nearly hydrostatic. This induces a micro-scale failure mode consisting in a matrix cavitation-induced debonding, driven by the Local Hydrostatic Stress (LHS) in the matrix. This was proposed as

the effective stress to be used for predicting crack initiation under a nearly transverse stress state [8].

Fig. 2. Schematic and example of off-axis crack formation by initiation of inclined micro-cracks in the matrix of a 45° ply

Also the delamination and fiber failure phenomena were analyzed from the microscopic point of view, revealing their interaction with off-axis cracks. Fatigue tests were carried out on glass/epoxy cross-ply laminates. Edge micrographs of the specimens were taken, revealing the typical scenario shown in Figure 3. Delamination was triggered by the presence of the off-axis cracks. A micro-scale delamination was indeed seen to form exactly at the moment of the off-axis crack formation and then to propagate at the interface [10].

The role that transverse cracks and delamination play on the failure of the fibers is clear from Figure 3. 0° fiber breaks are concentrated in the vicinity of the transverse crack tip and above the delamination, the growth of which leads to more and more fiber breaks, until a critical condition is reached.

Fig. 3. Example of delamination from a transverse crack tip with broken fibers

3 PREDICTION METHODOLOGY

According to the experimental observations, the fatigue life of a composite laminate has to be divided in different phases, each characterized by a dominating damage mode. Therefore, for predicting the fatigue behavior of a composite laminate, the initiation and evolution of each mechanism has to be predicted, together with its effect on the stress re-distribution and the

stiffness degradation. In particular, within a discrete damage mechanics framework, it is necessary to:

- i. Predict the cycles spent for crack initiation;
- ii. Describe the crack propagation and the crack density evolution until the saturation condition;
- iii. Predicting the cycles spent for the delamination initiation and propagation;
- iv. Predicting the cycles spent for the failure of the fibers and the final laminate failure.

For each mechanism (mainly off-axis cracks and delamination), the associated stiffness reduction must be predicted as well.

According to this strategy, a procedure for predicting the damage evolution in composite laminates has been developed by the authors, integrating the following predictive models and criteria:

- 1) A criterion for predicting the off-axis fatigue crack initiation under multiaxial stress states [8];
- 2) A mixed mode crack propagation criterion [11];
- 3) A model for predicting the crack density evolution under a generic multiaxial loading, also under variable amplitude conditions [12];
- 4) A fracture mechanics-based model for predicting the delamination growth, in combination with multiple crack initiation and propagation [13];
- 5) An analytical model for describing the stress re-distributions and the stiffness degradation in the presence of off-axis cracks and delamination [14];
- 6) A model for predicting the load bearing fiber failure, accounting for the stress concentrations caused by off-axis cracks and delamination [15].

The entire framework was validated by means of experimental data, revealing a very good agreement both in terms of damage evolution and stiffness loss. Some examples are reported in Figures 4 -6.

Fig 4. Validation of the procedure in terms of a) crack density and b) stiffness loss for a $[0/45_2/0/-45_2]_s$ plain laminate

Fig. 5. Validation of the procedure in terms of a) crack density and delaminated area ratio and b) stiffness loss for a $[0/90_2]_s$ laminate

Fig. 6. Prediction of the fatigue life of $[0_2/90_4]_s$ laminates through the complete modelling framework

4 APPLICATION TO NOTCHED LAMINATES

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The results shown so far were related to plain laminates, subjected to a uniform stress state. With the aim of using this strategy in the case of components with complicated geometry and loading conditions, all the developed models were implemented into a software tool (named RESCOMP – FLA) to be coupled with commercial Finite Element (FE) codes. The fatigue life can be simulated through a cycle jump approach. At each step, a linear-elastic FE analysis is carried out using layered shell elements. The results, in terms of element loads, are exported into the tool that analytically predicts the initiation and growth of damage events, as well as the element apparent elastic properties. These are then returned to the FE code as a starting point for the next cycle step. In this way it is possible to predict the damage evolution in components of any shape, that require the use of FE analyses for the assessment of the macro-scale stress distribution. At the same time the simulation is kept efficient as the discrete damage events are not physically present in the FE model, but only in a parallel database where the position of each damage mechanism is stored. As an example of application, the case of an open-hole cyclic test was considered. Tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted on $[0/90]_s$ and $[0/45_2/0/-45_2]_s$ glass/epoxy specimens in plain and notched configurations. The notched specimens were 40 mm wide, with a 8 mm and 16 mm diameter circular central hole. For both specimen types, the progression of damage throughout the fatigue life was monitored through periodic imaging and quantified based on crack initiation and crack density evolution. As expected, cracks predominantly originated along the notch flanks, with stress concentrations playing a crucial role in the damage process. Through the tests on plain specimens, fatigue crack initiation and propagation parameters were obtained and later used to predict the damage evolution in the notched laminates, through the analytical discrete damage approach. As an example, the damage evolution in a cross-ply laminate with a 8 mm central hole, as predicted by the tool and obtained from tests, is shown in Figure 7, showing a good agreement.

Fig. 7. Prediction of the fatigue life of $[0_2/90_4]_s$ laminates through the complete modelling framework

5 CONCLUSIONS

For an advanced and optimized design against fatigue of composite structures, tools to predict the onset and evolution of damage are required. In this work, a damage-based multiscale strategy was presented to predict the crack density evolution, the delamination growth and the associated stiffness loss in multidirectional laminates under cyclic loadings. To complete the framework and estimating the cycles to failure, a model to predict the failure of the load bearing plies has been also included.

The approach accounts for the interaction between different mechanisms. Criteria for the formation and growth of damage events were defined based on experimental observations at different length scales. The entire discrete damage approach was implemented into a software tool that the authors hope could be of help for improving the safety, the performance and the cost-efficiency of composite structures under cyclic loadings.

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